

ACCESS ICE SHEET MODEL SELECTION

FINAL REPORT

JULY 2024

Acknowledgements

A large number of people put an enormous amount of time into supporting and developing this process. We particularly wish to thank all the members of the Cryosphere Modelling Working Group and the time that they all freely gave to collating information on all the ice sheet models we reviewed, and providing input at each step of the process. We also wish to thank the ice sheet model developers who provided feedback - especially where we asked detailed, technical questions that took a while to answer! Every one of the developers was incredibly generous and it is a privilege to be able to work with them as part of the international ice sheet modelling community.

While we ended up deciding on only one ice sheet model to support, the ice sheet models that we reviewed are all excellent models. We learnt a lot about each of them and are looking forward to seeing - and participating in - the developments that occur in this discipline over the coming decades.

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We acknowledge the traditional owners of the land and waters on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth Systems we simulate.

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1 Executive summary

The Cryosphere Modelling Working Group (CMWG) is one of six community working groups supported by ACCESS-NRI. It was established in February 2023, and one of its first tasks was to establish a process for selecting an Ice Sheet Model (ISM) to be included in the ACCESS framework, with the ultimate goal of coupling ice sheet processes into the ACCESS Earth system model. ACCESS-NRI received an additional \$2,459,729 under the 2023 NCRIS Funding round to support ice sheet and coastal ocean modelling as part of an NCRIS-wide Coastal Research Infrastructure (CoastRI) Initiative.

The primary objective of ACCESS-NRI's 2023 funding is to couple an ISM of Antarctica and Greenland into ACCESS in order to improve decadal- to centennial-scale projections of global mean and regional sea level and climate change. Over the past year, the CMWG developed an ice sheet selection approach designed to meet this objective that was completed over three phases: (1) Community Consultation; (2) Assessment; (3) Model Selection. The outcome of the first two phases was a shortlist of three candidate ISMs that were deemed suitable for coupling with the ACCESS modelling framework to meet the primary objective. Those models were: Elmer/Ice, IcePack, and the Ice-sheet and Sea-level System Model (ISSM).

The third and final phase, the Model Selection, included an expert panel review of the consultation and assessment materials developed in the first two phases. The role of the expert panel was to assess each of the three shortlisted candidate ISMs against the primary objective and make a formal recommendation on which ice sheet model to incorporate into the ACCESS framework. The panel convened on May 13, 2024 and consisted of 8 members from the cryosphere and ACCESS modelling communities. It included the ACCESS-NRI Director (panel chair), CMWG co-chairs (3), a CMWG early career representative (1), and experts in ice sheet (1) and Earth system modelling (2).

The panel considered all the information available on the capability of each model, the input from community assessment and the risk profile of each model. At the conclusion of this deliberation it was clear that IcePack, while having some advantages, had less capacity and held greater risks than Elmer/Ice and ISSM. In most respects, Elmer/Ice and ISSM had similar capacity, similar existing Australian capability and an identical risk profile. The committee determined that ISSM has critical advantages over Elmer/Ice in modelling surface hydrology, forward and inverse capabilities for sliding laws, and data assimilation/adjoint capabilities. ISSM also has minor advantages in Holocene scale simulations capability, sea level coupling, and the size of the international developer community, while Elmer/Ice has minor advantages in fracture capabilities, rheology and existing coupling work in Australia. For these reasons, the committee **recommends that ACCESS-NRI adopt ISSM as its supported Ice Sheet Model.**

Two panel members dissented the choice of a single model. The dissenting opinions argued that ACCESS-NRI should support both ISSM and Elmer/Ice. The panel agreed that Elmer/Ice has existing research projects (including ISMIP7 preparation) that should not be interrupted by this decision. Furthermore, it was agreed that Elmer/Ice users will need support from ACCESS-NRI to switch to ISSM once new configurations can be supported.

The following material provides all the information relevant to assessing the shortlisted ISMs against the primary objective that was considered by the expert panel.

2 Background

The guiding principle for this task was to develop an open, transparent, and rigorous framework for deciding on an ice sheet model (ISM). To that end, the CMWG sought feedback on each step of the process from the Australian climate, ice sheet and Earth Systems communities formally, through the [Hive Forum](#) and at CMWG and other ACCESS-NRI Working Group meetings, and informally (e.g. direct contact). All documents were made freely available via the CMWG page on the Hive Forum. The processes were developed with reference to a report from a similar model selection activity (Associated Environmental Consultants, 2020).

2.1 Primary objective and selection criteria

The primary objective of coupling an Ice Sheet Model (ISM) of Antarctica and Greenland into ACCESS is to improve decadal- to centennial-scale projections of global mean and regional sea level and climate change. This primary objective was developed at the open CMWG meeting in November 2023. A period of consultation (see definition in [appendix A](#)) resulted in no feedback on the primary objective, which was adopted at the CMWG meeting in December 2023.

By definition, the primary objective focuses on ice sheet response timescales of decades to centuries. It follows that ISMs considered in this assessment may not have capabilities to simulate ice sheet evolution on glacial-interglacial timescales or longer, as required in paleoclimate applications. However, recognising the importance of understanding paleoclimate ice sheet-climate interactions, the capacity to capture ice sheet evolution on paleoclimate timescales is highly desirable.

To assess whether an ISM is fit-for-purpose against the primary objective, a set of selection criteria were developed at the open CMWG meeting in November 2023 and formally adopted after a period of consultation. The final set of selection criteria are listed in the ISM Ranking Table ([appendix B](#)).

The selection criteria were designated as *essential* or *desirable*, based on whether that criterion is necessary for the ISM to be considered fit-for-purpose. For example, for accurate and reliable simulations of ice sheet evolution on decadal timescales, an ISM should have inverse capabilities – rather than spin-up capabilities alone – to derive values for unknown ice sheet parameters. The designation as essential or desirable was derived by an open, online assessment conducted in early December 2023. From the 13 responses in the assessment, a criterion was designated as essential if agreed by the majority of respondents. A list of the final designation of each criterion is provided in the ISM Ranking Table ([appendix B](#)).

2.2 ISM selection procedure

The ISM selection procedure was developed at the open CMWG meeting in November 2023 and formally adopted in December 2023. A summary of the procedure is provided in figure 1 and outlined in more detail below.

Figure 1: Summary of the three key stages – community consultation, assessment and ISM selection – for advising on an ISM to be coupled into the ACCESS modelling framework.

Stage 1: Community consultation

Stage 1 consisted of two steps: (I) derive a list of candidate ISMs, and (II) define an approach to assess each ISM against the selection criteria.

Step I. The candidate ISMs that were included in the assessment are summarised in [appendix C](#). This list includes: all ISMs currently used within Australia; all ISMs currently being coupled into ESMs by other international modelling centres; and other ISMs that are commonly used in the international ice sheet modelling community or that have sizeable user bases (defined as at least 6 identifiable users).

Step II. At the November 2023 CMWG, it was agreed to adopt the assessment approach derived by Associated Environmental Consultants for the selection of a hydrologic model for the Okanagan Basin Water Board (Associated Environmental Consultants, 2020). This approach involved the development of an ISM Ranking Table ([appendix B](#)), with the list of selection criteria, their designation as essential or desirable, an importance weighting, and definitions of what constitutes “poor” or “excellent” performance against each criterion.

The final importance weightings and the definitions of poor and excellent scores in the Ranking Table were developed by the co-chairs of the CMWG, in consultation with members of the expert panel who have background knowledge of ice sheets and ice sheet modelling. The importance weightings reflect the significance of each criterion as a measure of ISM capability with respect to the primary objective.

Stage 2: Assessment

Stage 2 consisted of three levels of preliminary, developer and community assessments.

The preliminary assessment aimed to generate a shortlist of candidate ISMs that satisfy the essential criteria. To make this assessment, information on each candidate ISM was compiled, and the developers were contacted to assess the developer support criteria. A summary of the ISMs excluded at this step is included in [appendix C](#). Three ISMs were shortlisted: Elmer/Ice, IcePack, and ISSM.

The developer assessment consisted of a questionnaire that was sent to the developers of the shortlisted ISMs to populate information about the ISMs relevant to the selection criteria that might not be freely available online (e.g. future development plans). Of the three shortlisted ISMs, two of the developers provided written feedback on the questionnaire, and one developer was interviewed via zoom. Following the first two levels of assessment, summaries of the shortlisted ISM capabilities were developed ([appendix D](#)), which included the necessary information to score the ISMs against each selection criterion.

The community assessment aimed to generate an initial ranking of the shortlist. The assessment was open – via links on the Hive Forum – to anyone in the Australian ice sheet, climate and Earth Systems communities, including those affiliated with ACCESS-NRI. A second expert assessment was elicited from experts (predominantly ice sheet modellers) within the international community who do not have a conflict of interest (i.e., are not users of any ISM in the shortlist). Respondents were provided with the ISM Ranking Table and the ISM summaries. A summary of the community assessment was provided at the Expert Panel meeting.

Stage 3: ISM selection

Stage 3 consisted of the expert panel meeting and a final recommendation. The aim of the expert panel meeting was to arrive at consensus (or majority vote) of an ISM that: (I) is fit-for-purpose against the primary objective; (II) has a low risk profile; and (III) the panel agrees would be a suitable ISM for inclusion into the ACCESS modelling framework. This final recommendation is based on the outcome of the expert panel meeting.

3 Community Assessment Results

The open community assessment ran from Monday 29th April until Thursday 9th May 2024.

Respondents were provided with the ISM Ranking Table (with associated criteria and scoring metric from poor-excellent), as well as summaries of each candidate ice sheet model. Respondents were asked to score each ice sheet model against each criterion using the information provided or respond “unable to assess” if not enough information was provided. Respondents were requested to provide justification for each of their choices.

A total of 12 respondents completed the community assessment (Table 1; note that 3 respondents were also members of the expert panel). Additional direct correspondence (email) was received from 10 further respondents.

Table 1: Community assessment respondents overview.

Organisation	Count	Background/expertise	Count
CSIRO	1	Ice Sheet Modeller	9
Monash University	5	Ice Sheet Scientist	1
University of Tasmania	6	Climate/Earth Systems Scientist	2

3.1 Overall results

Table 2 below shows the aggregated results of the Community Assessment across all selection criteria, as well as the results from each category. The categories 1-5 refer to the following 5 categories from the ISM Ranking Table ([appendix B](#)): (1) Model capabilities; (2) Model physics; (3) Input/output and initialisation; (4) Flexibility and modularity; (5) Accessibility, useability and institutional support.

The aggregated results below are normalised by the maximum value that could have been achieved for each criterion as a function of the number of responses and the importance weighting (ISM Ranking Table; [appendix B](#)). Importance weightings, derived by a majority vote of a subset of the Expert Panel, ranged from 1-5, with 5 representing the most important and 1 representing the least important. For example, for a criterion with an importance weighting of 4 (out of 5), if 10 respondents gave numerical responses to the criterion for one ISM that totalled 42 (i.e., less than the maximum score of 50), then the overall score of that ISM for the criterion would have been $(4 / 5) * 42 / 50 = 0.67$.

ISSM received the highest overall score for the Community Assessment as well as the highest score for each category, followed by Elmer/Ice. IcePack consistently received the lowest overall and category scores.

Table 2: Overview summary of Community Assessment results.

	Maximum score	Elmer/Ice	ISSM	IcePack
Overall	20.4	16.8	18.6	13.1
Category 1	5.8	5.3	5.5	4.1
Category 2	3.4	2.7	3.0	1.8
Category 3	2.4	1.5	2.1	1.5
Category 4	2.8	2.2	2.4	1.5
Category 5	6	5.1	5.5	4.2
# respondents top ranked*		1/8	7/8	0/8

*Excludes responses from expert panellists and any incomplete assessments.

The sections that follow present the scores for each ISM against each selection criteria, grouped by category. In each heatmap, the maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

3.2 Model capabilities

Community assessment scores for the “**Model capabilities**” grading criteria are presented below in Figure 2. Respondent justifications are summarised in Table 3.

Figure 2: Community assessment scores for the “Model capabilities” against each selection criteria. The maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

Table 3: Summary of respondent justifications for the “Model capabilities” grading criteria.

Criterion	Feedback/evaluation
Variable, unstructured, horizontal resolution (mesh)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General consensus that all models had similar skill • Slightly lower rankings reflect less flexibility in setup
Higher-order physics	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contains most physics options <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full stokes not available (disadvantage) • Comment about the correctness of the implementation of SIA (re: importance of variation in rheology with depth due to temperatures)
Capable of regional- and continental-scale configurations for both Antarctica and Greenland, and potentially glacier-scale configurations	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well established for both regional and continental domains <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Untested for Antarctica and Greenland. <p>Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well established for both regional and continental domains. One respondent suggested previous experience was difficult when used for small domains.
Capable of transient simulations across decadal to centennial timescales	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well established on these timescales <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered untested for centennial-scale timescales <p>Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well established on these timescales. One respondent suggested from previous experience that Elmer/Ice was difficult.
Capable of transient simulations across longer timescales	<p>This criteria received a broad range of responses.</p> <p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ranked more highly by some as it is the only model to have demonstrated millennial-scale runs in HO. <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ranked more/less highly due to potential for computational efficiency at paleo timescales.
Adaptive mesh	<p>All models are able to adapt the mesh over the course of a transient simulation, but adaptive meshing is not widely used. Question from one respondent about whether adaptive meshing numerics in all models is mass and energy conserving.</p> <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ranked consistently lower due to adaptive meshing only feasible for shorter timescales.
Performance in benchmarking experiments that test fundamental behaviour, including community-established protocols	<p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally ranked lower due to not having participated in many MIPs (younger model).

3.3 Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget

Community assessment scores for the “Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget” grading criteria are presented below in Figure 3. Respondent justifications are summarised in Table 4.

Figure 3: Community assessment scores for the “Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget” against each selection criteria. The maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

Table 4: Summary of respondent justifications for the “Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget” grading criteria.

Criterion	Feedback/evaluation
Grounding line and ice shelf evolution, and buttressing	ISSM & Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Similar capabilities including sub-grid parameterisations. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Does not have sub-grid parameterisations.
Sliding relations	ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Considered to have slightly more capability, with all sliding laws available in both inverse and forward model runs. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Less development as it is a more recent model.
Hydrofracture and surface hydrology	ISSM & IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Both models are currently developing surface hydrology. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hydrofracture model being implemented - currently available for 1D cases.
Surface mass budget	ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked more highly due to the greater number of options of surface mass balance schemes. <p>One respondent commented that the positive degree day model (in both Elmer/Ice and ISSM) is not necessarily advantageous due to its lacking a strong physical basis; strong support by multiple respondents for improved surface mass budget methods available through coupling.</p>
Ice shelf/glacier calving	ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternatively ranked higher for having many options available, and lower for having fewer options in terms of fracture capabilities. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternatively ranked higher for having better fracture capabilities, and lower for fewer available options. One participant commented that coupling with the high resolution discrete element model (HiDEM) is not yet feasible on a continental scale and on timescales of relevance to our primary objective. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower as it has fewer options.
Deformation and rheology	Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked highest due to most extensive development in tensor rheologies. However, tensor rheologies are not yet feasible at continental scale and timescales of relevance to our primary objective. Scalar flow relation for anisotropic ice is available ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scalar flow relation for anisotropic ice is available IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One respondent said “I’ve given up on assessing IcePack because I think it lacks key features and is too untested to realistically consider for this purpose.”

3.4 Input/output & initialisation

Community assessment scores for the “Input/output & initialisation” grading criteria are presented below in Figure 4. Respondent justifications are summarised in Table 5.

Figure 4: Community assessment scores for the “Input/output & initialisation” against each selection criteria. The maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

Table 5: Summary of respondent justifications for the “Input/output & initialisation” grading criteria.

Criterion	Feedback/evaluation
Data assimilation for initialisation with transient data assimilation in scope	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked most highly due to exact adjoint and forward-inverse capabilities for all sliding laws. <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Offers numerous user advantages as it is a python package with potential for functions including gradient descent; however, requires further development for these capabilities to be realised.
Automatic differentiation (AD)	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked most highly as it is the only model to have this direct capability. <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potentially has substantial flexibility for development here due to its python base.
Conventional data format	<p>There was some confusion evaluating this criteria resulting in some variability in rankings, but mean ranking similar for all models. All models have similar capabilities for i/o (coupling with other climate modules) and outputs for visualisation.</p>

3.5 Flexibility & modularity

Community assessment scores for the “Flexibility & modularity” grading criteria are presented below in Figure 5. Respondent justifications are summarised in Table 6.

Figure 5: Community assessment scores for the “Flexibility & modularity” against each selection criteria. The maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

Table 6: Summary of respondent justifications for the “Flexibility & modularity” grading criteria.

Criterion	Feedback/evaluation
Coupling with other components of the climate system including ocean, atmosphere, land surface	<p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked lower due to fewer number of models coupled. <p>Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked higher due to greater number of ocean models coupled. <p>None of the shortlisted ISMs have been coupled with anything other than ocean models at this stage (i.e., not with atmosphere or land surface models)</p>
Subglacial hydrology (including sediment evolution and transport)	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked highly for having multiple options. <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower as it has had less development. <p>Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked highly for having multiple options. ● Received an extra rank vote from one respondent as it includes groundwater capabilities.
Solid Earth (including glacial isostatic adjustment)	<p>ISSM & Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked similarly for capability. Elmer/Ice has viscoelastic model, which is advantageous for solid Earth deformation. <p>IcePack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower by some respondents (due to less demonstrated capability), and equal to or higher by 3 respondents due to potential opportunities through Firedrake/ANU efforts.
Far-field sea level changes associated with regional-scale ice sheet and glacier mass changes	<p>ISSM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked highest as it has sea level modules built-in. <p>IcePack & Elmer/Ice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No development of sea level modules.
Additional feedback	<p>A number of respondent comments questioned how the ice sheet models might interact with atmosphere or land surface models, exchanging back relevant data fields, and also regarding potential conflicts of responsibility (e.g., regarding surface albedo, surface energy balance, surface hydrology, etc.).</p>

3.6 Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support

Community assessment scores for the “Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support” grading criteria are presented below in Figure 6. Respondent justifications are summarised in Table 7.

Figure 6: Community assessment scores for the “Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support” against each selection criteria. The maximum score (i.e., normalised by the importance weighting) achievable for each selection criterion is shown in the top row; the Elmer/Ice results are shown in the second row; the ISSM results are shown in the third row; and the IcePack results are shown in the bottom row.

Table 7: Summary of respondent justifications for the “Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support” grading criteria.

Criterion	Feedback/evaluation
Open and accessible code	IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility as a python-based code ranked as both advantageous or disadvantageous by respondents. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked slightly lower by some respondents due to requiring building the whole Elmer package.
Code management for community development	All models generally ranked very highly.
Size and approachability of user community	ISSM & Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked very highly. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower due to lower user base
Relationship with developers and evidence of their willingness/capacity to engage/support	ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked very highly. ● Some comments suggest a more distributed developer base than the other ISMs, which is advantageous. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower due to less use in Australia and less strong existing relationships. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked very highly.
Computational efficiency	ISSM & Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked very highly. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternatively ranked highly due to potential for efficiency, and lower due to lack of demonstration.
Ease of code use	ISSM & IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked similarly highly. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked lower due to the known steep learning curve required.
Active development plan from developers	ISSM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked the highest. ● Some comments suggest a more distributed developer base than the other ISMs, which is advantageous. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower due to less evidence/limited track record. Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternatively ranked higher for having a clear development plan and lower where the development plan did not align clearly with our primary objectives.
Additional feedback on Australian use / institutional support	ISSM & Elmer/Ice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generally ranked highest for strong use in Australia. IcePack: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ranked lower due to a limited track record.

3.7 Direct feedback

Additional direct correspondence (email) was received from 10 further respondents. Key points conveyed included:

- Priority should be to select a model that best interfaces with ACCESS model components and coupler *now*, given the time taken for other ESM centres to couple ISMs.
- Important to have a model that a community forms around - code flexibility, code standards, ability to run in various configurations etc seem to be at least as important as any specific current capability.
- Code documentation is important
- Importance of having an ACCESS Earth System model with a cryosphere, to keep ACCESS as a first rank ESM
- Key elements are to get accurate sub-shelf melt and iceberg calving
- Elmer/Ice:
 - HiDEM coupling option a strength for icebergs (although feedback from the community assessment notes that this is currently not feasible at continental scales for decadal-centennial timescales).
- IcePack:
 - Less developed than the other two candidate models but this might allow ACCESS-NRI to have more influence in future development.
- ISSM:
 - Sea-level change capability a big advantage

4 Risk assessments

The risk assessments that follow were adapted from the PESTLE framework for risk analysis. These assessments are draft and may include post-mitigation risks that are uncertain. Final risk assessments will be discussed and decided by the expert panel.

Definitions of likelihood, consequence and risk are as follows in Figure 7.

	Consequence				
Likelihood	Insignificant	Minor	Significant	Major	Severe
Almost certain	Medium	High	Very high	Extreme	Extreme
Likely	Medium	Medium	High	Very high	Extreme
Moderate	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Very high
Unlikely	Very low	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Rare	Very low	Very low	Low	Medium	Medium

Figure 7: PESTLE framework used for the risk assessments in the Ice Sheet Model (ISM) selection process.

4.1 Elmer/Ice

Table 8: Risk assessment for the Elmer/Ice ice sheet model candidate.

Category	Potential risk	Likelihood	Consequence	Overall risk	Mitigation	Post mitigation risk
Political/ Organisational	Collaboration failure with developers	Unlikely	Major	Medium	Relationship with multiple developers/contributors currently exists; ACCESS-NRI strengthen existing and build new relationships with multiple developers/contributors	Low
	Developer organisation failure: CSC is company majority-owned/funded by the Finnish government and international (e.g. Australia-Finland) political relations could impact delivery/support of Elmer/Ice	Unlikely	Severe	High	4 core developers (all at CSC) but 10 contributors to development spread across multiple different institutes	Low
	One or more institutions go in a different direction to meet this primary objective	Unlikely	Significant	Medium	Research institutes adopt ACCESS recommendations because of the quality of the ISM process. Research institutes secure funding for research applications of ACCESS.	Low
Financial	Developer funding failure: CSC is company majority-owned/funded by the Finnish government. If CSC were to lose funding or be discontinued, would lose primary development source	Moderate	Major	Very high	Evidence of developers (including CSC) accessing multiple funding streams, and additional developers and contributors are spread across multiple institutes	Low
	Developers require financial support from	Unlikely	Minor	Low	Evidence of developers (including CSC) accessing multiple funding streams, and track	Very low

	ACCESS-NRI that is unable to be provided				record of in-kind support with Australian users	
Demographic	Developer/s leave/retire without replacement	Moderate	Minor	Medium	Multiple developers/contributors exist and ACCESS-NRI can build user/contributor base through training	Very low
Technological	Model is not fit-for-purpose (against primary objective, adhering to selection criteria)	Rare	Major	Medium	Procedure ACCESS-NRI developed for determining model has been open, transparent and rigorous, involving ice sheet modellers and experts	Low
	Model becomes obsolete in changing technological landscape. E.g. Elmer/Ice requires building Elmer, which is a multiphysical simulation software and may impact flexibility of Elmer/Ice in approaching ice sheet-specific problems	Moderate	Major	High	Developers have a track record of developing best practice code; future development plan includes "keeping up" with emerging technology (e.g. GPU capabilities currently under development)	Low (on a 10-15 year timeframe)
	Delays in reaching a scientifically accurate, fully coupled Earth system model	Moderate	Major	High	Learn from mistakes of other communities. There are 14 other communities working on coupling between ice sheet and Earth Systems models. We have an existing connection through ISMIP7 working group on ISM-ESM coupling. Elmer/Ice has a track record of being coupled with other parts of the climate system.	Medium
Legal	Licence software infringement	Rare	Significant	Low	All library dependencies are currently open source	Very low
Strategic	Model user base declines/fails and fewer active developers/con	Unlikely	Significant	Medium	Australian-based development could support ongoing use	Low

	tributors					
Operational	Australian community does not have required expertise to couple and use model	Moderate	Significant	Medium	Support from developers (including CSC) and strong capabilities/expertise in software engineering and ice sheet dynamics exist within Australian community	Low

4.2 IcePack

Table 9: Risk assessment for the IcePack ice sheet model candidate.

Category	Potential risk	Likelihood	Consequence	Overall risk	Mitigation	Post mitigation risk
Political/ Organisational	Collaboration failure with developers (given no relationship currently exists between Australian users and developers)	Moderate	Major	High	ACCESS-NRI strengthen existing and build new relationships with multiple developers/contributors	Medium (on a <5 timeframe)
	Developer organisation failure (IcePack developers currently supported through university system)	Unlikely	Severe	High	A few developers exist and are spread across multiple institutes; developer base likely to increase if IcePack is coupled into ACCESS	Low
	One or more institutions go in a different direction to meet this primary objective	Likely	Major	Very high	Research institutes adopt ACCESS recommendations because of the quality of the ISM process. Research institutes secure funding for research applications of ACCESS.	High
Financial	Developer funding failure: developers are supported through multiple funding streams (e.g. university and US National Science Foundation)	Unlikely	Severe	High	Evidence of developers accessing multiple funding streams; developers are spread across a few different institutes	Low

	Developers require financial support from ACCESS-NRI that is unable to be provided	Unlikely	Minor	Low	Evidence of developers (including CSC) accessing multiple funding streams, and track record of in-kind support with Australian users	Very low
Demographic	Developer/s leave/retire without replacement	Moderate	Major	High	A few developers/contributors exist (i.e. there is a small degree of redundancy) and ACCESS-NRI can build user/contributor base through training	High (on a <5 timeframe)
Technological	Model is not fit-for-purpose (against primary objective, adhering to selection criteria)	Rare	Major	Medium	Procedure ACCESS-NRI developed for determining model has been open, transparent and rigorous, involving ice sheet modellers and experts	Low
	Model becomes obsolete in changing technological landscape	Moderate	Major	High	IcePack is a relatively new model (<3 years old) built on flexible codebase that is designed to be versatile	Low (on a 10-15 year timeframe)
	Delays in reaching a scientifically accurate fully coupled Earth system model	Likely	Major	Very high	Learn from mistakes of other communities. There are 14 other communities working on coupling between ice sheet and Earth Systems models. We have an existing, connection through ISMIP7 working group on ISM-ESM coupling.	High
Legal	Licence software infringement	Rare	Significant	Low	All library dependencies are currently open source	Very low
Strategic	Model user base declines/fails and fewer active developers/contributors (note: IcePack user base is much smaller than Elmer/Ice and ISSM)	Moderate	Significant	Medium	Australian-based development could support ongoing use	Medium
Operational	Australian community does not have required expertise to couple and use model	Moderate	Significant	Medium	Support from developers and strong capabilities/expertise in software engineering and ice sheet dynamics exist within Australian community	Low

4.3 ISSM

Table 10: Risk assessment for the ISSM ice sheet model candidate.

Category	Potential risk	Likelihood	Consequence	Overall risk	Mitigation	Post mitigation risk
Political/ Organisational	Collaboration failure with developers	Unlikely	Major	Medium	Relationship with multiple developers/contributors currently exists; ACCESS-NRI strengthen existing and build new relationships with multiple developers/contributors	Low
	Developer organisation failure (ISSM developers supported through multiple systems including both university and government)	Unlikely	Severe	High	12 core developers and 50 contributors to development spread across multiple institutes and countries	Low
	One or more institutions go in a different direction to meet this primary objective	Unlikely?	Significant	Medium	Research institutes adopt ACCESS recommendations because of the quality of the ISM process. Research institutes secure funding for research applications of ACCESS.	Low
Financial	Developer funding failure: developers are supported through multiple funding streams (e.g. university, US National Science Foundation, private tech companies, and government)	Unlikely	Severe	High	Evidence of developers accessing multiple funding streams, and large developer and contributor base are spread across multiple institutes and countries	Low
	Developers require financial support from ACCESS-NRI that is unable to be provided	Unlikely	Minor	Low	Evidence of developers accessing multiple funding streams, and track record of in-kind support with Australian users	Very low

Demographic	Developer/s retire without replacement	Moderate	Minor	Medium	Multiple developers/contributors exist and ACCESS-NRI can build user/contributor base through training	Very low
Technological	Model is not fit-for-purpose (against primary objective, adhering to selection criteria)	Rare	Major	Medium	Procedure ACCESS-NRI developed for determining model has been open, transparent and rigorous, involving ice sheet modellers and experts	Low
	Model becomes obsolete in changing technological landscape.	Moderate	Major	High	Developers have a track record of developing best practice code (including multiple codebases – both C/C++ and julia for different applications); future development plan includes “keeping up” with emerging technology (e.g. GPU capabilities currently under development)	Low (on a 10-15 year timeframe)
	Delays in reaching a scientifically accurate fully coupled Earth system model	Moderate	Major	High	Learn from mistakes of other communities. There are 14 other communities working on coupling between ice sheet and Earth Systems models. We have an existing, connection through ISMIP7 working group on ISM-ESM coupling. Elmer/Ice has a track record of being coupled with other parts of the climate system.	Medium
Legal	Licence software infringement	Rare	Significant	Low	All library dependencies are currently open source	Very low
Strategic	Model user base declines/fails and fewer active developers/contributors	Unlikely	Significant	Medium	Australian-based development could support ongoing use	Low
Operational	Australian community does not have required expertise to couple and use model	Moderate	Significant	Medium	Support from developers and strong capabilities/expertise in software engineering and ice sheet dynamics exist within Australian community	Low

5 Expert Review

5.1 Overview

The third and final phase, the Model Selection, included an expert panel review of the consultation and assessment materials developed in the first two phases. The role of the expert panel was to assess each of the three shortlisted candidate ISMs against the primary objective and make a formal recommendation on how to best incorporate ice sheet modelling into the ACCESS framework. The panel convened on May 13, 2024 and consisted of 8 members from the cryosphere and ACCESS modelling communities. It included the ACCESS-NRI Director (panel chair), CMWG co-chairs (3), a CMWG early career representative (1), and experts in ice sheet (1) and Earth system modelling (2). Full panel detail can be found in Table 11.

Table 11: Expert panel attendees.

Chair	Andy Hogg	Director, ACCESS-NRI
CMWG* co-chair	Felicity McCormack	Senior Research Fellow, Monash University
CMWG* co-chair	Ben Galton-Fenzi	Senior Scientist, Australian Antarctic Division
CMWG* co-chair	Chen Zhao	ARC DECRA Fellow, University of Tasmania
Early Career Representative	Lawrence Bird	PhD Student, Monash University
Ice sheet expert	Poul Christoffersen	Professor, University of Tasmania
Paleoclimate/Earth systems modelling expert	Katrin Meissner	Professor, UNSW
CSIRO Representative and Earth systems modelling expert	Rachel Law	Senior Principal Research Scientist, CSIRO
Rapporteur	Kelsey Druken	Associate Director and CMWG* Liaison, ACCESS-NRI
Observer	Martin Dix	Associate Director, ACCESS-NRI
Observer	Mike Tetley	Research Software Engineer, ACCESS-NRI (Ice Sheet Modelling Team Lead, commencing July 2024)

*Cryosphere Modelling Working Group (CMWG)

5.2 Recommendation

The panel considered all the information available on the capability of each model, the input from community assessment and the risk profile of each model. At the conclusion of this deliberation it was clear that IcePack, while having some advantages, had less capacity and held greater risks than Elmer/Ice and ISSM. In most respects, Elmer/Ice and ISSM had similar capacity, similar existing Australian capability and an identical risk profile.

The panel then reviewed the community assessment results and compiled a list of where the top 2 candidate models differed in the selection criteria (summarised in the ISM grading table). The criteria identified are shown in table 12 below.

The panel unanimously agreed that both ISSM and Elmer/Ice would make excellent choices for ACCESS-NRI to adopt and support. However, it was also agreed that supporting a single model would be the most effective use of ACCESS-NRI resources. The committee determined that ISSM has critical advantages over Elmer/Ice in modelling surface hydrology, inverse capabilities for sliding laws, and data assimilation/adjoint capabilities, including automatic differentiation. These critical advantages are highlighted by bold text in Table 12. ISSM also has minor advantages in paleoclimate capability, sea level coupling, and the size of the international developer community, while Elmer/Ice has minor advantages in fracture capabilities, rheology and existing coupling work in Australia. For these reasons, the committee **recommends that ACCESS-NRI adopt ISSM as its supported Ice Sheet Model.**

Table 12: Differences in Selection Criteria between Elmer/Ice and ISSM, grouped by category. The most critical differences are in bold text.

Category	Selection Criteria
Model capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Paleoclimate modelling
Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sliding laws (with data assimilation) ● Surface mass balance ● Surface hydrology ● Fracture capabilities ● Australian experience in ocean coupling with ice shelves ● Deformation and rheology ● Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA)
Input/output & initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data assimilation ● Automatic differentiation ● Coding language (e.g., Fortran vs. C++)
Flexibility & modularity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sea-level coupling
Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ease of use ● Size of the developer community

The panel endorsed the recommendation that ISSM is the preferred model. Two panel members dissented the choice of a single model. The dissenting opinions argued that ACCESS-NRI should support both ISSM and Elmer/Ice. The panel agreed that Elmer/Ice has existing research projects (including ISMIP7 preparation) that should not be interrupted by this decision. Furthermore, it was agreed that Elmer/Ice users will need support from ACCESS-NRI to switch to ISSM once new configurations can be supported.

The selected model should not stop ongoing initiatives using other models. ACCESS-NRI's purpose in funding this work is to add support, not to remove support for initiatives that are underway. There will be science questions and research projects using Elmer/Ice that should continue until such time that ACCESS-NRI has developed capability exceeding existing research groups.

ACCESS-NRI will seek endorsement from their Advisory Board to adopt and support the recommended model - ISSM.

Appendix A: acronyms and definitions

Acronyms

ACCESS Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator

AD Automatic differentiation

ESMF Earth System Modelling Framework

HPC High performance computing

ISM Ice Sheet Model

MIP Model Intercomparison Project

NCI National Computational Infrastructure

NUOPC National Unified Operation Prediction Capability

Definitions

Fit-for-purpose ISM satisfies the essential criteria outlined in the ISM Ranking Table that were developed to assess each ISM against the primary objective

Developer questionnaire Includes questions to obtain further information on the ISM fit-for-purpose that might not otherwise be available online. Developer feedback went into the shortlisted model summaries found in the ISM Summaries ([appendix D](#)).

Consultation A set period (length of time variable) within which feedback is requested on a particular item. Consultation periods are always advertised on the Hive Forum, and may also be advertised during CMWG meetings, other ACCESS-NRI Working Group meetings, and informally within the climate, ice sheet, and Earth Systems communities in Australia.

Appendix B: ISM Ranking Table

Category	Selection criteria	Essential (Y/N)	Importance Weighting	Poor Score (1) definition	Excellent Score (5) definition
Model capabilities	Variable, unstructured, horizontal resolution (mesh) <i>Unstructured mesh with refinement in regions critical for dynamics (e.g. grounding zones and shear margins)</i>	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Few meshing options available - Limited flexibility in adjusting the mesh 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable mesh with enhanced resolution at the coastline is possible - Multiple meshing options available - Mesh can be optimised based on a large range of variables (e.g. observational and error fields, location, vertex length)
	Higher-order physics <i>Stokes and depth-averaged approximation to Stokes are desirable, but not sufficient on their own</i>	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited options for higher-order physics, i.e.: only Stokes OR only Higher Order approximations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Options for both higher-order (Stokes) and approximated physics (Higher Order or depth-averaged approximations)
	Capable of regional- and continental-scale configurations for both Antarctica and Greenland, and potentially glacier-scale configurations	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional- or continental-scale configurations are difficult to set up and have not yet been achieved. - Remeshing between different configurations is difficult or not possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional- to continental-scale configurations for Greenland and Antarctica are straightforward to setup and have already been achieved - Options exist for remeshing between different configurations
	Capable of transient simulations across decadal to centennial timescales	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No or limited evidence of performance in transient simulations on decadal-centennial timescales, e.g. no evidence of, or not accurate or reliable simulations of ice sheet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence of performance in transient simulations on decadal-centennial timescales, e.g. accurately and reliably simulating ice sheet evolution over historical timescales

				evolution over recent past	
	Capable of transient simulations across longer timescales <i>Millennial; glacial-interglacial timescales</i>		2	No or limited evidence of performance in transient simulations on: - Millennial timescales - Glacial-interglacial timescales	Evidence of performance in transient simulations on: - Millennial timescales - Glacial-interglacial timescales
	Adaptive mesh <i>Transient mesh adaptation, including refinement appropriate to changing dynamics</i>		3	- No inbuilt transient mesh adaptation - No or limited capacity for mask updates during transient simulation (i.e. cannot change between ice or no ice/ocean, etc.) - Regridding not mass conserving	- Inbuilt transient mesh adaptation - Full capacity to update the mask during transient run (i.e. can change between ice or no ice/ocean, etc) - Adaptive meshing scheme is mass and energy conserving - Fully online mesh adaptation OR offline implementation is computationally efficient
	Performance in benchmarking experiments that test fundamental behaviour, including community-established protocols <i>Includes but not limited to: ISMIP, MISMIP, MISOMIP/+, ISMIP-HOM</i>		2	- ISM has not participated in a wide variety of MIPs - Limited evidence with which to assess ISM performance against other ISMs - Not consistent track record of ISM contributing to international modelling developments and standards	- ISM has participated in a wide variety of MIPs - Large body of evidence with which ISM performance can be assessed relative to other ISMs - Strong track record of ISM contributing to international modelling developments and standards
Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass budget	Grounding line and ice shelf evolution, and buttressing <i>How well do models simulate changes to ice shelves and</i>	Y	5	- Limited flexibility in defining grounding line location and sub-ice-shelf melting and changes due to buttressing - No evidence of or performs inconsistently in	- Flexibility in numerical approach to defining the grounding line location and sub-ice-shelf melting (e.g. full element, sub-grid parameterisation) and changes due to buttressing - Performs consistently well in benchmarking

	<i>influences on grounding line position and buttressing</i>			benchmarking experiments against established targets OR does not satisfy agreed benchmarking standards (e.g. grounding line migration opposite direction to expected)	experiments against established targets OR satisfies agreed benchmarking standards (e.g. grounding line migration and ice shelf thickness changes in expected direction and magnitude) - Substantial evidence for capacity to simulate expected flow dynamics associated with climatic change, e.g. rapid grounding line retreat, instabilities and tipping-points
	Sliding relations <i>Multiple sliding laws are available; ideally should include at least the following: Coulomb (or variations, e.g. regularised Coulomb), Schoof, Weertman, Budd</i>	Y	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No strong physical basis for existing schemes - Performs consistently poorly at OR does not satisfy agreed benchmarking standards related to sliding dynamics (e.g. observed changes in velocity; feedbacks between grounding line migration and ice flow; dynamic thinning) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong physical basis in existing schemes - Performs consistently well at OR satisfies agreed benchmarking standards related to sliding dynamics (e.g. observed changes in velocity; feedbacks between grounding line migration and ice flow; dynamic thinning)
	Hydrofracture and surface hydrology		2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No inbuilt hydrofracture/surface hydrology OR - Existing schemes perform poorly compared with observations OR - Lack of strong physical basis in existing schemes - Code development unfeasible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong physical basis in existing schemes - Developers and code are amenable to future development and/or improvement*
	Surface mass budget		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No inbuilt surface mass budget schemes OR - Existing schemes perform poorly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong physical basis in existing schemes - Developers and code are amenable to future development and/or improvements*

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> compared with observations OR - Lack of strong physical basis in existing schemes - Code development unfeasible 	
	Ice shelf/glacier calving		3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No inbuilt ice shelf calving schemes OR - Existing schemes perform poorly compared with observations OR - Code development unfeasible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ice shelf front migration is possible - Multiple calving schemes available - Developers and code are amenable to future development and/or improvement*
	Deformation and rheology		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing schemes perform poorly compared with observations OR - Code development unfeasible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing schemes perform well compared with observations - Developers and code are amenable to future development and/or improvement*
Input/output & initialisation	<p>Data assimilation for initialisation with transient data assimilation in scope</p> <p><i>Spinup initialisation alone not sufficient</i></p>	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full adjoint option not available - Limited flexibility in modification of cost function and coefficients - Single field input into cost function (e.g. only velocity) - Transient data assimilation not supported and/or difficult to implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inversion using the full adjoint available - Considerable flexibility in modification of cost function and coefficients - Multi-field input into cost function (e.g. velocity, surface elevation) - Performs consistently in capturing both current state of the ice sheet and trends - Inversion capabilities available for multiple sliding laws - Transient data assimilation is available - Developers and code are amenable to future development/improvement*
	Automatic differentiation (AD)		2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AD is not already inbuilt - No future plans to incorporate AD - Code not amenable to future development of AD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AD is inbuilt - AD is fully functioning and evidence of its use in peer-reviewed publications - Developers and code amenable to future development/improvement*

					t* OR use of external AD software is possible
	Conventional data format		3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output data format difficult to access (e.g. requires proprietary or non-standard software to access) - No or unclear metadata 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Output data format accessible - Metadata are clear, such that experiments are reproducible
Flexibility & modularity	Coupling with other components of the climate system including ocean, atmosphere, land surface	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No evidence of successful coupling to ocean, atmosphere or land surface modules - Limited flexibility in code base for coupling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has been successfully coupled to other ocean, atmosphere or land surface models - Framework for coupling well documented - Developers and code amenable to coupling* - Compatible in current form to couple with ACCESS via NUOPC/ESMF
	Subglacial hydrology (including sediment evolution and transport)		4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No evidence of successful coupling to subglacial hydrology modules - Limited flexibility in code base for coupling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has successfully incorporated subglacial hydrology modules or coupling to models and evidence of its use in peer-reviewed publications - Framework for coupling well documented - Developers and code amenable to coupling* - Sediment evolution and transport possible or code amenable to future work
	Solid Earth (including glacial isostatic adjustment)		2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No evidence of successful coupling to solid Earth modules - Limited flexibility in code base for coupling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has successfully incorporated solid Earth modules or coupling to solid earth models. - Framework for coupling well documented - Developers and code are amenable to coupling*
	Far-field sea level changes associated with regional-scale ice sheet and glacier mass changes		3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No regional far-field sea level budgets OR ability to perform sea level fingerprinting - Limited flexibility in code base for coupling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has regional far-field sea level budgets AND/OR ability to perform sea level fingerprinting - Framework is well documented - Developers and code base are amenable to future

					improvements to sea level/fingerprinting treatment, including full coupling with ice dynamics (if not already possible)*
Accessibility, useability, development potential, and Australian institutional support	Open and accessible code	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code or parts of the code are not open source or rely on libraries or compilers that are not open source - Code is poorly documented - Complex and non-standard libraries with limited support and development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All code (source, associated libraries, and post-processing) is open source and well documented* - Standard libraries with regular development
	Code management for community development	Y	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor or outdated version control system - Little evidence of active development - Unclear process for code updates - Code updates are not implemented in a timely manner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code is managed on open source modern version control system (Git, SVN, etc) - Evidence of active development - Clear process for code updates - Code updates are implemented in a timely manner*
	Size and approachability of user community	Y	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User community is small AND/OR relatively inactive - User community is concentrated in one institute/country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User community is sizeable, active (e.g. as measured by engagement, workshops, papers, etc.), and helpful* - User community is distributed across many countries - Regular* workshops are held
	Relationship with developers and evidence of their willingness/capacity to engage/support	Y	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No relationship with developers - Developers are unlikely to be able to provide ongoing support - Developer community is small (relies on a few key developers) - Developer community is concentrated and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Track record of strong relationship with developers - Developers are likely to be able to provide ongoing support - Developer community is large - Developer community is distributed across institutes/countries/funding streams

				relies on few funding streams	- Developers can assist with code scaling and optimisation on NCI, evidenced by when that has occurred
Computational efficiency	Y	5		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not parallelised for HPC - No evidence of benchmark on HPC systems OR - Evidence of poor model efficiency on HPC system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parallelised for HPC - Evidence for benchmarking on HPC systems - Model highly efficient in parallel computing
Ease of code use		2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No user guide - No or limited post-processing and visualisation toolboxes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User guide exists, is comprehensive and informative and updated regularly - Comprehensive post-processing and visualisation toolbox
Active development plan from developers		3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No evidence of development plan - Poor track record in completing significant development - Development plan is unlikely to lead to substantial improvements in model capacity to meet our primary objective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development plan available and clear - Evidence of ability to carry out significant development - Development plan is likely to lead to substantial improvements in model capacity to meet our primary objective
Institutional support and/or expert knowledge within Australian community to guide coupling; Australian user community participation in international collaborations and/or projects		1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No users in Australian community OR - User/s have little familiarity with underlying codebase - User/s unlikely to be available for support during coupling timeframe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple users in Australian community with institutional support - User/s with history of ice sheet model code development - Strong track record in Australian user contributions to international collaborations and/or projects - User/s community likely to be present for duration of coupling timeframe

Notes

* Statements marked with an asterisk are subjective and based on the track record of the ISM/development team, where assessable. These statements are made in the context of determining whether the ISM is fit-for-purpose against the primary objective.

Exclusions: All candidate models shortlisted necessarily satisfy the essential criterion of being mass and energy conserving; hence, we have excluded that criterion from the table above. None of the candidate models shortlisted satisfy the desirable criterion of standardisation in variable names and units. Given that no such internationally-agreed standardisation exists, this criterion is moot.

Appendix C: Candidate ISMs and inclusion category

ISM	Inclusion category	Exclusion justification (with respect to the essential selection criteria)
SICOPOLIS	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not have unstructured meshing
AISMPALEO	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not include inversion capabilities
BICICLES	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not have higher order dynamics - Does not have multiple sliding laws
CISM	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not include inversion capabilities - Does not have unstructured meshing
Elmer/Ice	Included	
Grisli	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not meet minimum developer support criterion
IcePack	Included	
IMAUICE	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not include inversion capabilities
ISSM	Included	
KORI	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not meet minimum developer support criterion
MALI	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not meet minimum developer support criterion
PISM	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not include inversion capabilities - Does not have unstructured meshing
Úa	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Not open source codebase (MATLAB)
WAVI	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics - Does not have unstructured meshing
ISM inbuilt into MOM6 (unnamed)	Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not include higher order dynamics

Appendix D: ISM Summaries

Overview + summary of each shortlisted model

Elmer/Ice

Category	Selection criteria	Capability
Model capabilities	Variable, unstructured horizontal resolution (mesh) <i>Unstructured mesh with refinement in regions critical for dynamics (e.g. grounding zones and shear margins)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Option for variable horizontal resolution with mesh refinement at grounding line - Regular and unstructured meshing available - Adaptive mesh based on any model field (e.g. velocity, surface slope, strain rate, etc) - Mesh optimisation is configurable based on a wide range of parameters (e.g. vertex length, etc)
	Higher-order physics <i>Stokes and depth-averaged approximation to Stokes are desirable, but not sufficient on their own</i>	Physics available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full Stokes - Blatter-Pattyn - Shallow Shelf Approximation - Shallow Ice Approximation
	Adaptive mesh <i>Transient mesh adaptation, including refinement appropriate to changing dynamics</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient refinement available (i.e. mesh size updates during transient simulation) - Mask updates during transient runs using level set method
	Performance in community-established benchmarking experiment <i>Includes but not limited to: ISMIP, MISMIP, MISOMIP/+, ISMIP-HOM</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model has been extensively tested and benchmarked, including, but not limited to, in MIP experiments - Performance in benchmarking experiments generally consistent with other ISMs and expected dynamics, although some notable exceptions due to parameterisations, numerics and methodologies have been reported (e.g. Sun et al., 2020) - Contributed to ISMIP-HOM, MISMIP+, MISOMIP, ISMIP6 Greenland and Antarctica, SHMIP, CalvingMIP, initMIP
	Capable of regional- and continental-scale configurations for both Antarctica and Greenland, and potentially glacier-scale configurations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence for model configuration on any domain, including Antarctica and Greenland, as well as regional configurations (catchments, ice caps, glaciers, etc) - Remeshing between continental and regional configurations possible
	Capable of transient simulations across multiple timescales, including glacial and interglacial timescales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient simulations using Stokes model on decadal-centennial timescales - Transient simulations using SSA on multi-centennial to millennial timescales

Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass balance	Grounding line dynamics <i>Solves mechanical contact problem; multiple options for defining grounding line location (full element, sub-grid parameterisation); transient grounding lines</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grounding line dynamics using mechanical contact for Stokes and hydrostatic equilibrium for SSA (configured for transient simulations) - Different sub-grid parametrizations for melt, that impact grounding line migration rate (full/no melt on partially-floating cells; sub-element melt parameterisation)
	Ice shelf evolution <i>Model is capable of simulating ice shelf evolution (e.g. through geometry changes)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ice front evolution with level-set function - Evolving geometry is allowed with ice thickness, free surface solvers - Grounding line evolution based on grounding line schemes
	Sliding relations <i>Multiple sliding laws are available; ideally should include at least the following: Coulomb (or variations, e.g. regularised Coulomb), Schoof, Weertman, Budd</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weertman, Budd, Coulomb, regularised Coulomb, Tsai, Schoof - Different sub-grid parameterisations for friction (no friction on partially-floating cells; full friction on partially-floating cells; sub-element friction interpolation) - All sliding laws are available for forward simulations; only linear Weertman is available for inverse simulations
	Hydrofracture and surface hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No surface hydrology module - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Surface mass balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive Degree Day model (PDD); well-established model for which there is strong physical basis - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Ice shelf calving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crevasse-depth method available (vertical + 3D) - Coupling to discrete element model (HiDEM) possible - Visco-elastic linear elastic fracture mechanics in development - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Deformation and rheology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variety of rheologies (e.g. UMAT for plasto-elasticity) based on experimental results (i.e. strong physical basis) - Tensor and scalar rheologies for anisotropic ice - Cold firn rheology - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
Input/output & initialisation	Data assimilation with transient data assimilation in scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data assimilation via self-adjoint (not full/exact adjoint) - Some flexibility in cost functions (linear, logarithmic); full flexibility in modifying cost function coefficients - Cost function based on surface velocity or ice thickness fields

	<i>Spinup initialisation alone not sufficient</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Track record of evidence that inversion provides good match to current state of ice sheet, but no option to explicitly match to trends (e.g. thickness trend) - Transient data assimilation not available - Model code base generally amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Automatic differentiation (AD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not available - Not in scope for future development
	Conventional data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MPIRUN uses binary format - Option to output final data in any format, gridded and ungridded - Unstructured VTK for visual output - Full flexibility for adding metadata to NetCDF outputs
Flexibility & modularity	Ease of coupling with other components of the climate system including ocean, atmosphere, land surface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has been coupled with ocean models: ROMS, FVCOM, NEMO - Coupling with climate model IPSL-CM under development - ESMF compliant and compatible in current form to couple with ACCESS via NUOPC
	Subglacial hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GlaDS, dual-layer model, and permafrost-groundwater models available - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Solid Earth (including glacial isostatic adjustment, sediment evolution and transport)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viscoelastic solver for solid Earth - Simple local lithosphere/relaxing asthenosphere model - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Capable of projecting and incorporating far-field sea level changes associated with regional-scale ice sheet and glacier mass changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not available - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
Accessibility, useability and development potential	Open and accessible code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code is documented* - Codebase fortran with some C modules - Relies on Elmer base code to be compiled (Elmer is finite element software for multi-physics problems; i.e. not simply ice sheet model), which is highly complex and generally relies on developer support to build - Standard and non-standard libraries (some licences required for specific libraries: GPL v2 and LGPL maintained by Thomas Zwinger)
	Code management for community development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code available via GitHub - Evidence of active development through GitHub issue feature (i.e. also clear process for code updates) - Code issues generally implemented in timely manner* (responses from developers usually within days; fixes might take longer depending on complexity and development timeframe)

	Size and approachability of user community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ~100 active users - User community mainly concentrated in Europe (Finland, France, Germany, UK, Sweden); users also in Australia, China, Japan, Canada, US - Annual workshops and side meetings at major conferences - Active online forum for community engagement and active developer responses for user support (responses from developers usually within hours)
	Relationship with developers and their willingness/capacity to engage/support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong developer support of Australian users, with regular co-authorship on publications - Development mainly funded by Finland government through CSC; ongoing development contingent on this funding - CSC oversee the Elmer codebase; 4 developers of Elmer; 1 most active developer of Elmer/Ice - 10 active contributors to Elmer/Ice - Verbal support for Elmer/Ice development into ACCESS - Developer (Thomas Zwinger) maintains Elmer/Ice on NCI gadi
	Ease of code use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Userguide freely accessible; generally well documented* - Some level of guidance recommended for non-expert/beginner user*; examples/short tutorials available in online materials - Post-processing tools available (Paraview, python, matlab, XIOS) - Active forum to support users
	Active development plan from developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elmer/Ice has 10+ years of development and is one of world's leading ice sheet models - Development plan by request to core development team at Finnish IT Centre for Science (CSC) - Development ongoing through funded projects and other projects at CSC. E.g. development for GPU compatibility in next 5-10 years - Options to work directly with CSC for development that supports ACCESS priorities
	Computational efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model benchmarked for parallel performance - Strong scalability based on tests using Greenland domain (Gagliardini et al., 2013)
	Institutional support and/or expert knowledge within Australian community to guide coupling; Australian user community participation in international collaborations and/or projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 users in Australia (collective ~12 years of usage within the Australian community), supported for the duration of the coupling timeframe - Contribution of users to international collaborations and/or projects, including ISMIP6 and MISOMIP1 - Code development within the Australian community

Icepack

Category	Selection criteria	Capability
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Model capabilities	Variable, unstructured horizontal resolution (mesh) <i>Unstructured mesh with refinement in regions critical for dynamics (e.g. grounding zones and shear margins)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Option for variable horizontal resolution with mesh refinement at grounding line - Regular and unstructured meshing available - Adaptive mesh based on any function or model field (e.g. velocity, surface slope, strain rate, or other function, etc) - Mesh optimisation is configurable (e.g. vertex length, etc)
	Higher-order physics <i>Stokes and depth-averaged approximation to Stokes are desirable, but not sufficient on their own</i>	<p>Physics available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blatter-Pattyn higher order model - Shallow-Shelf (Shelfy-Stream) Approximation - Shallow Ice Approximation - Hybrid physics available - Stokes not funded or currently under development (planned for development in next few years)
	Adaptive mesh <i>Transient mesh adaptation, including refinement appropriate to changing dynamics</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient refinement (i.e. mesh size can update during transient simulation, but feasible for shorter, i.e. 50-100 year timescales; fine-resolution transient updates not planned) - Mask updates during transient runs using level set method
	Performance in community-established benchmarking experiment <i>Includes but not limited to: ISMIP, MISMIP, MISOMIP/+, ISMIP-HOM</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contributed to MISMIP+ - Model has been tested and benchmarks, although relatively new model, so fewer examples of performance against other ISMs and community standards - No reported issues
	Capable of regional- and continental-scale configurations for both Antarctica and Greenland (and potentially glacier-scale configurations?)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model can be in-principle be configured on any domain; however, development required for whole-Antarctic and whole-Greenland domains (no evidence of continental-scale ice sheet model configurations to date) - Remeshing between continental and regional configurations possible
	Capable of transient simulations across multiple timescales, including glacial and interglacial timescales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient simulations using higher-order approximation model on decadal-centennial timescales - Transient simulations using other model physics on multi-centennial to millennial timescales
Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass balance	Grounding line dynamics <i>Solves mechanical contact problem; multiple options for defining grounding line location (full element, sub-grid parameterisation); transient grounding lines</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grounding line dynamics assume hydrostatic equilibrium - No sub-grid parametrizations implemented yet

	Ice shelf evolution <i>Model is capable of simulating ice shelf evolution (e.g. through geometry changes)</i>	Ice front evolution available Evolving geometry is allowed with ice thickness, surface solvers Grounding line movement based on grounding line scheme
	Sliding laws <i>Multiple sliding laws are available; ideally should include at least the following: Coulomb (or variations, e.g. regularised Coulomb), Schoof, Weertman, Budd</i>	- Weertman, Schoof
	Hydrofracture and surface hydrology	- Surface hydrology module available - No hydrofracture module - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Surface mass balance (SMB)	- Schemes currently in development (funded) - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Ice shelf calving	- Calving and rifting module available - More advanced calving models currently in development (funded) - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Deformation and rheology	- Scalar rheology (Glen flow relation) implemented - Transient evolution of damage field available - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
Input/output & initialisation	Data assimilation with transient data assimilation in scope <i>Spinup initialisation alone not sufficient</i>	- Data assimilation via adjoint (full/exact adjoint not available) - Some flexibility in cost functions (linear, logarithmic); full flexibility in modifying cost function coefficients - Cost function takes only velocity as input - Track record of evidence that adjoint-based inversion provides good match to current state of ice sheet, but no option to explicitly match trends - Transient data assimilation available - Model code base generally amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Automatic differentiation (AD)	- Not implemented
	Conventional data format	- HDF5 outputs - Full flexibility for adding metadata to NetCDF outputs
Flexibility & modularity	Ease of coupling with ocean, atmosphere, solid Earth, land surface	- Coupling with ROMS via FISOC currently underway - Not ESMF compliant

	Subglacial hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subglacial hydrology module in development (funded) - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Solid Earth (including glacial isostatic adjustment, sediment evolution and transport)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solid Earth modules available in Firedrake (underlying code base) and coupling is relatively straightforward* (note: Firedrake solid Earth models under development by Australian community) - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Capable of projecting and incorporating far-field sea level changes associated with regional-scale ice sheet and glacier mass changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No sea level equation or fingerprint - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
Accessibility, useability and development potential	Open and accessible code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code is documented - Codebase python - Relatively straightforward to build; requires Firedrake code - Standard and non-standard libraries; all open source
	Code management for community development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code available via GitHub - Evidence of active development through GitHub issue feature (i.e. also clear process for code updates) - Code issues generally implemented in timely manner (although relatively new model so less extensive demonstration)
	Size and approachability of user community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small user base* - Weekly open in-person and online meetings
	Relationship with developers and their willingness/capacity to engage/support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development funded by NSF and NASA, across 3 institutes in US - 4 core developers in US - Verbal support for development into ACCESS
	Ease of code use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Userguide freely accessible; documentation in development (relatively new model <3 years old) - User guide with examples provided for non-expert/beginner users; ease of use is one of primary motivations for developing the model - Some post-processing and visualisation tools available (jupyter notebooks on GitHub)
	Active development plan from developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development plan by request to core development team at University of Washington - Current funded developments include: subglacial hydrology; SMB; ice shelf calving

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No development plan for GPU compatibility, although GPU compatibility being developed in underlying codebase Firedrake - Icepack has <3 years of development - Options to work directly with developers to support ACCESS priorities
	Computational efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional configurations efficient (Shapero et al., 2021); development and benchmarking required for whole-Antarctic and whole-Greenland domains
	Institutional support and/or expert knowledge within Australian community to guide coupling and/or involvement with stand alone MIP experiments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 user in Australia (<1 year of usage); multiple users of Firedrake in Australia, including development of solid Earth modules

ISSM

Category	Selection criteria	Capability
Model capabilities	Variable, unstructured horizontal resolution (mesh) <i>Unstructured mesh with refinement in regions critical for dynamics (e.g. grounding zones and shear margins)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Option for variable horizontal resolution with mesh refinement at grounding line - Regular and unstructured meshing available - Adaptive mesh based on any function or model field (e.g. velocity, surface slope, strain rate, or other function etc) - Mesh optimisation is configurable based on a wide range of parameters (e.g. vertex length, anisotropy between adjacent elements, etc)
	Higher-order physics <i>Stokes and depth-averaged approximation to Stokes are desirable, but not sufficient on their own</i>	Physics available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full Stokes - Blatter-Pattyn higher order model - Shallow-Shelf (Shelfy-Stream) Approximation - Shallow Ice Approximation - L1L2 - Hybrid physics available
	Adaptive mesh <i>Transient mesh adaptation, including refinement appropriate to changing dynamics</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient refinement available (i.e. mesh size updates during transient simulation) - Mask updates during transient runs using level set method
	Performance in community-established benchmarking experiment <i>Includes but not limited to: ISMIP, MISOMIP, MISOMIP+, ISMIP-HOM</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model has been extensively tested and benchmarked, including, but not limited to, in MIP experiments - Performance in benchmarking experiments generally consistent with other ISMs and expected dynamics, although relatively higher model drift has occurred that may be linked to initialisation procedure (e.g.

		<p>when data assimilation by inversion is used, then drift is generally higher; this is a feature common to ISMs that have inverse capabilities)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contributed to ISMIP-HOM, MISMIP, MISMIP3D, MISMIP+, MISOMIP, ITMIX, ITMIX-2, SeaRISE, ABUMIP, LARMIP, ISMIP6 Greenland and Antarctica, SHMIP, CalvingMIP, initMIP
	<p>Capable of regional- and continental-scale configurations for both Antarctica and Greenland (and potentially glacier-scale configurations?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence for model configuration on any domain, including Antarctica and Greenland, as well as regional configurations (catchments, ice caps, glaciers, etc) - Remeshing between continental and regional configurations possible
	<p>Capable of transient simulations across multiple timescales, including glacial and interglacial timescales</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transient simulations using Stokes model on decadal-centennial timescales - Transient simulations using other model physics on multi-centennial to millennial timescales - Longest published run using Blatter-Pattyn (3D) physics is over the Holocene (11,000 years; Cuzzone et al., 2019)
<p>Model physics fundamental to ice flow and mass balance</p>	<p>Grounding line dynamics</p> <p><i>Solves mechanical contact problem; multiple options for defining grounding line location (full element, sub-grid parameterisation); transient grounding lines</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grounding line dynamics using mechanical contact for Stokes and hydrostatic equilibrium for SSA (configured for transient simulations); options also for sub-element, soft or aggressive migration - 5 different sub-grid parameterisations for melt, that impact grounding line migration rate (full/no melt on partially-floating cells; multiple sub-element melt parameterisations)
	<p>Ice shelf evolution</p> <p><i>Model is capable of simulating ice shelf evolution (e.g. through geometry changes)</i></p>	<p>Ice front evolution with level-set function</p> <p>Evolving geometry is allowed with ice thickness, free surface solvers</p> <p>Grounding line movement based on grounding line schemes</p>
	<p>Sliding laws</p> <p><i>Multiple sliding laws are available; ideally should include at least the following: Coulomb (or variations, e.g. regularised Coulomb), Schoof, Weertman, Budd</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weertman, Budd, Coulomb, regularised Coulomb (multiple versions), Tsai, Schoof, Shakti - 3 options for sub-grid parameterisations (no friction on partially-floating cells; full friction on partially-floating cells; 2 sub-element friction interpolations) - All sliding laws are available for both forward and inverse simulations
	<p>Hydrofracture and surface hydrology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two surface hydrology modules funded and in development (MONARCH, SaDS) - No hydrofracture module - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*

	Surface mass balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - >10 SMB models available, including Positive Degree Day model (PDD; well-established model for which there is strong physical basis) and SMB model for debris-covered glaciers - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Ice shelf calving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crevasse-depth method available (vertical + 3D) - Linear elastic fracture mechanics method available - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Deformation and rheology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scalar rheologies implemented for isotropic and anisotropic ice - Static damage calculation (including using inverse methods) available; transient damage evolution funded and in development - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements (code base is amenable to tensor flow relation if needed)*
Input/output & initialisation	Data assimilation with transient data assimilation in scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data assimilation via adjoint (full/exact and self--full-adjoint available) - Some flexibility in cost functions (linear, logarithmic); full flexibility in modifying cost function coefficients - Cost function can be modified to take any field as input - Track record of evidence that adjoint-based inversion provides good match to current state of ice sheet, but no option to explicitly match trends - Transient data assimilation available in AD and non-AD mode (see below) - Model code base generally amenable to future developments / improvements
	<i>Spinup initialisation alone not sufficient</i>	
	Automatic differentiation (AD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automatic differentiation fully validated with checkpointing - Enables inversion to match any field based on any other input (i.e. allows explicitly matching trends), and is fully validated for long (20-30 year) runs - Currently restricted to smaller domains (max 200,000 elements) - NOVO project to continue development of AD funded and underway for next 5 years with developers of CoDiPack, including extending to larger domains (200,000+ elements)
	Conventional data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MPIRUN uses binary format (input-output) - Option to output final data in any format, gridded and ungridded - Full flexibility for adding metadata to NetCDF outputs

Flexibility & modularity	Ease of coupling with ocean, atmosphere, solid Earth, land surface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has been coupled with ocean models: ISSM-MITgcm (offline coupling; online coupling funded and in development), GEOS5 (online coupling) - FESOM coupling in development - New German climate model natESM testing ongoing (first phase passed) - ESMF compliant and compatible in current form to couple with ACCESS via NUOPC
	Subglacial hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple (6) hydrology models available including: GlaDS, dual-layer model - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Solid Earth (including glacial isostatic adjustment, sediment evolution and transport)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viscoelastic solver for solid Earth in development - Elastostatic adjustment model available - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
	Capable of projecting and incorporating far-field sea level changes associated with regional-scale ice sheet and glacier mass changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sea level equation including gravitation, viscoelasticity, and rotation feedbacks - Model code base amenable to future developments / improvements*
Accessibility, useability and development potential	Open and accessible code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code is documented - Codebase C/C++ with some fortran modules; julia code base in development - Relatively straightforward* to build across different operating systems - Standard (PETSC, Mumps) and non-standard libraries (triangle, M1QN3); all open source
	Code management for community development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code available via SVN and currently under migration to GitHub - Evidence of active development through trak issue feature (i.e. also clear process for code updates) - Code issues generally implemented in timely manner* (responses from developers usually within days; fixes might take longer depending on complexity and development timeframe)
	Size and approachability of user community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ~150 active users across 12 countries (Norway, Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Netherlands, UK, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Korea, China) - Annual workshops and side meetings at major conferences - Active online forum for community engagement and active developer responses for user support (responses from developers usually within hours)
	Relationship with developers and their willingness/capacity to engage/support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong developer support of Australian users, with regular co-authorship on publications - Development funded across multiple countries and institutes including: USA, UK, New Zealand, Korea, Germany, Norway, Australia

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 12 core developers across multiple countries and institutes - 50 active contributors to development - Verbal support for ISSM development into ACCESS - Developers can assist with code scaling and optimisation on ACCESS HPC (track record of existing support)
Ease of code use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Userguide freely accessible; generally well documented* - Extensive* user guide with examples provided for non-expert/beginner users - - Extensive* post-processing and visualisation tools (via Matlab or python)
Active development plan from developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISSM has 10+ years of development and is one of world's leading ice sheet models - Development plan by request to core development team at: Dartmouth College, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, or through other funded projects - Funded developments currently underway include: AD capability for larger domains (200,000+ elements); effect of freshwater on ocean-induced melt downstream of grounding line; seawater intrusion; viscoelastic solver for solid Earth; subglacial hydrology models applied to large domains (full Antarctic and full Greenland ice sheets); MITgcm online coupling - Development for GPU compatibility funded and anticipated in next 5-10 years - Options to work directly with developers to support ACCESS priorities
Computational efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model benchmarked for parallel performance - Strong scalability based on multiple studies for idealised and whole-Greenland domains (Fischler et al., 2021; Habbal et al., 2017; Larour et al., 2012)
Institutional support and/or expert knowledge within Australian community to guide coupling; Australian user community participation in international collaborations and/or projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 users in Australia (collective ~13 years of usage), with ongoing institutional support (supported beyond coupling timeframe within ACCESS) - Contribution of users to international collaborations and/or projects - 1 active contributor to development in Australia

Notes

* Statements marked with an asterisk are subjective and based on the track record of the ISM/development team, where assessable. These statements are made in the context of determining whether the ISM is fit-for-purpose against the primary objective.

Exclusions: All candidate models shortlisted necessarily satisfy the essential criterion of being mass and energy conserving; hence, we have excluded that criterion from the table above. None of the candidate models shortlisted satisfy the desirable criterion of standardisation in variable names and units. Given that no such internationally-agreed standardisation exists, this criterion is moot.

References

Associated Environmental Consultants, 2020. *Final Report for the Okanagan Basin Water Board: Okanagan Hydrologic Models for Long-term Water Planning & Management.*

https://www.obwb.ca/docs/obwb_report_2020-okanagan-hydrologic-modelling.pdf